

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND ANALYTICAL REVIEWS (IJRAR) | IJRAR.ORG

An International Open Access, Peer-reviewed, Refereed Journal

E-ISSN: 2348-1269, P-ISSN: 2349-5138

The Board of
International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)
Is hereby awarding this certificate to

Dr. Nitya Nand Pandey

In recognition of the publication of the paper entitled

Trial before a court of session under Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita 2023: A comprehensive analysis

Published In IJRAR (www.ijrar.org) UGC Approved - Journal No : 43602 & 7.17 Impact Factor

Volume 12 Issue 2 May 2025, Date of Publication: 09-May-2025

PAPER ID : IJRAR25B2792

Registration ID : 312258

R.B. Joshi

EDITOR IN CHIEF

UGC and ISSN Approved - Scholarly open access journals, Peer-reviewed, and Refereed Journals, Impact factor 7.17 (Calculate by google scholar and Semantic Scholar | AI-Powered Research Tool) , Multidisciplinary, Monthly Journal

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND ANALYTICAL REVIEWS | IJRAR

An International Scholarly, Open Access, Multi-disciplinary, Indexed Journal

Website: www.ijrar.org | Email: editor@ijrar.org | ESTD: 2014

Manage By: IJPUBLICATION Website: www.ijrar.org | Email ID: editor@ijrar.org

Trial before a court of session under Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita 2023: A comprehensive analysis

Dr. Nitya Nand Pandey, Dean, School of Law, G. H. Rasoni University Amravati, Maharashtra

Abstract:

A new criminal law procedure named Bharatiya Nagrik Suraksha Sanhita 2023 was enacted in the year of 2023 by Indian Parliament and the same was came in to force on 1st of July 2024. It replaced Criminal Procedure Code 1973 and Criminal Procedure Code 1973 did replace the Criminal Procedure Code 1898. If we discuss the changes that have taken place in the criminal procedural law since 1898, then a book of several volumes can be written. For now, in this article of mine, we have discussed what changes have been made in the session trial and how many reforms are still required.

Introduction:

The first criminal procedure code, in India, produced in the year of 1882 and it was published on 1 July 1898 and further commenced on 1 July 1898¹. In that code, there was 480 sections classified in to 35 chapters and the basic feature was that the magistrate had been given both the powers i.e. judicial and administrative. Later on, the new criminal procedure code was enacted in the year of 1973. In this code there was 484 sections classified in to 37 chapters. The need to provide speedy justice and the desire to remove procedural complexity gave birth to new criminal laws. The new criminal procedural law has total 531 Section classified in to 39 chapters.

If we are talking about the Code of 1898, Court of Session included a Metropolitan Court of Session. But in the Code of 1973 and in BNSS, the Session court and metropolitan court is quite different. Metropolitan magistrate is equivalent to Magistrate first class and the session court is know as the district and session court.

248	Trial to be conducted by Public Prosecutor
249	Opening case for prosecution
250	Discharge
251	Framing of charge
252	Conviction on plea of guilty
253	Date for Prosecution evidence
254	Evidence for prosecution
255	Acquittal
256	Entering upon defence
257	Arguments
258	Judgment of acquittal or conviction
259	Previous conviction
260	Procedure in cases instituted under sub-section (2) of section 222

¹ <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/110773890/>

Trial to be conducted by Public Prosecutor²

In every trial before a Court of Session, the prosecution shall be conducted by a Public Prosecutor. It doesn't mean that complainant has not a right to appoint his private advocate. He can, but the private advocate would be subject to subordinate to public prosecutor.

Opening case for prosecution³

If the accused is on bail and appears on a summon issued by session court or if he is in jail and warrant is issued by superintendent of jail and he brought the accused before the Court, in pursuance of a commitment of the case under section 232, or under any other law for the time being in force, the prosecutor shall open his case by describing the charge brought against the accused, and stating by what evidence he proposes to prove the guilt of the accused.

At this stage prosecution will try to establish his case and prima-facie it appears to court that the crime has done none other than accused appeared before the court.

Application by accused⁴

When the court of chief judicial magistrate finds that the matter is exclusive triable by court of session, he shall commit the matter before session court under section 232 of BNSS 2023 and within 60 days from such committal of case, the accused may prefer an application for discharge.

Discharge of accused⁵

After receiving the application of accused and upon consideration of the record of the case, and the documents submitted therewith, and after hearing the submissions of the accused and the prosecution in this behalf, If the Judge considers that there is not sufficient ground for proceeding against the accused, he shall discharge the accused and record his reasons for so doing.

Transfer the case for magistrate trial⁶

After such consideration and hearing as aforesaid, if the Judge is of opinion that there is ground for presuming that the accused has committed an offence which the case is not exclusively triable by the Court of Session, he may, frame a charge against the accused and, by order, transfer the case for trial to the Chief Judicial Magistrate, or any other Judicial Magistrate of the first class, and direct the accused to appear before such court, on such date as he deems fit, and thereupon such Magistrate shall try the offence in accordance with the procedure for the trial of warrant-cases instituted on a police report.

When the matter is not transferred for Magistrate Trial⁷

If the Session Court is of opinion that the case is exclusively triable by session Court, he shall frame in writing a charge against the accused within a period of **60 days** from the date of first hearing on charge and the charge shall be read and explained to the accused present either physically or through audio-video electronic means and the accused shall be asked whether he pleads guilty of the offence charged or claims to be tried.

252. Conviction on plea of guilty⁸

If the accused pleads guilty, the Judge shall record the plea and may, in his discretion, convict him thereon. In this provision, the court has option that he may convict the accused or not. If it appears to court that such acceptance of guilt is not voluntarily or it has been given under threat, promise or fear, the court can proceed for trial.

² Section 248 of BNSS 2023

³ Section 249 of BNSS 2023

⁴ Section 250 of BNSS 2023

⁵ Section 250 of BNSS 2023

⁶ Section 251 of BNSS 2023

⁷ Section 251 of BNSS 2023

⁸ Section 252 of BNSS 2023

Process for attendance of Prosecution evidence⁹

If the accused refuses to plead, or does not plead, or claims to be tried or he plead guilty but court does not convict him, the Judge shall fix a date for the examination of prosecution witnesses, and on the application of the prosecution, he may issue any process for compelling the attendance of any witness or the production of any document or other thing.

Evidence for prosecution¹⁰

On the date so fixed, the Judge shall proceed to take all such evidence as may be produced in support of the prosecution. **Provided that** evidence of a witness under this sub-section may be recorded by audio-video electronic means. If any witness is a public servant, his statement may be taken through audio-video electronic means.

The Judge may, in his discretion, permit the cross-examination of any witness to be deferred until any other witness or witnesses have been examined or recall any witness for further cross-examination.

Acquittal of Accused¹¹

After taking the evidence for the prosecution, examining the accused and hearing the prosecution and the defence on the point, If the Judge considers that there is no evidence which establishes beyond reasonable doubt that the accused committed the offence, the Judge shall record an order of acquittal.

Entering upon defence¹²

If the prosecution has proved beyond reasonable doubt that the accused has committed the offence and so, the accused is not acquitted under section 255, he shall be called upon to enter on his defence and adduce any evidence he may have in support thereof. If the accused puts in any written statement, the Judge shall file it with the record.

Application of Accused for issuing the process

If the accused applies for the issue of any process for compelling the attendance of any witness or the production of any document or thing, the Judge shall issue such process. But in certain circumstances, the court may not issue the process i.e. it is made for the purpose of vexation or delay or for defeating the ends of justice.

Final Arguments from Both Side¹³

When the examination of the witnesses (if any) for the defence is complete, the prosecutor shall sum up his case, and the accused or his advocate shall be entitled to reply. If any point of law is raised by the accused or his advocate, the prosecution may, with the permission of the Judge, make his submissions with regard to such point of law.

Where the Court is satisfied that a case pending before him, involves a question as to the validity of any Act, Ordinance or Regulation or of any provision contained in an Act, Ordinance or Regulation, the determination of which is necessary for the disposal of the case, and is of opinion that such Act, Ordinance, Regulation or provision is invalid or inoperative, but has not been so declared by the High Court to which that Court is subordinate or by the Supreme Court, the Court shall state a case setting out its opinion and the reasons therefor, and refer the same for the decision of the High Court. Any Court making a reference to the High Court may, till the pending the decision of the High Court, either commit the accused to jail or release him on bail to appear when called upon.¹⁴

⁹ Section 253 of BNSS 2023

¹⁰ Section 254 of BNSS 2023

¹¹ Section 255 of BNSS 2023

¹² Section 256 of BNSS 2023

¹³ Section 257 of BNSS 2023

¹⁴ Section 436 of BNSS 2023

Judgment of acquittal or conviction¹⁵

After hearing arguments and points of law (if any), the Judge shall give a judgment in the case, as soon as possible, within a period of 30 days from the date of completion of arguments, which may be extended to a period of 45 days for reasons to be recorded in writing.

If the accused is convicted, the Judge shall, unless he proceeds in accordance with the provisions of section 401¹⁶, hear the accused on the questions of sentence, and then pass sentence on him according to law.

259. Previous conviction¹⁷

In a case where a previous conviction is charged under the provisions of sub-section (7) of section 234, and the accused does not admit that he has been previously convicted as alleged in the charge, after he has convicted the said accused under section 252 or section 258, the Judge may take evidence in respect of the alleged previous conviction, and shall record a finding thereon.

Provided that no such charge shall be read out by the Judge nor shall the accused be asked to plead thereto nor shall the previous conviction be referred to by the prosecution or in any evidence adduced by it, unless and until the accused has been convicted under section 252 or section 258.

Procedure in cases instituted under sub-section (2) of section 222¹⁸**a. Procedure of trial**

Where any complaint has been filled by public prosecutor regarding the complain made of President of India or Governor of any State or Administrator of any Union Territory and cabinet minister under section 222 clause 2 before the court of session, Court of Session shall try the case in accordance with the procedure for the trial of warrant-cases instituted otherwise than on a police report before a Court of Magistrate.

b. Examination of victim

The person against whom the offence is alleged to have been committed shall be examined as a witness for the prosecution unless the Court of Session, for reasons to be recorded, otherwise directs.

c. Trial in camera

Every trial under this section shall be held in camera, if either party thereto so desires, or if the Court thinks fit so to do.

d. Show cause notice for false accusation

If, in any such case, the Court discharges or acquits all or any of the accused and is of opinion that there was no reasonable cause for making the accusation against them or any of them, it may, by its order of discharge or acquittal, direct the person against whom the offence was alleged to have been committed to show cause why he should not pay compensation to such accused or to each or any of such accused, when there are more than one. But it is not applicable in the matter of President, the Vice-President or the Governor of a State or the Administrator of a Union territory.

e. Compensation for false accusation

The Court shall record and consider any cause which may be shown by the person so directed, and if it is satisfied that there was no reasonable cause for making the accusation, it may, for reasons to be recorded, make an order that compensation to such amount not exceeding **5000 rupees**, as it may determine, be paid by such person to the accused or to each or any of them.

¹⁵ Section 258 of BNSS 2023

¹⁶ Order to release on probation of good conduct or after admonition.

¹⁷ Section 259 of BNSS 2023

¹⁸ Section 260 of BNSS 2023

f. Recovery of compensation

Compensation awarded under sub-section (4) shall be recovered as if it were a fine imposed by a Magistrate.

g. Civil or criminal action

No person who has been directed to pay compensation under sub-section (4) shall, by reason of such order, be exempted from any civil or criminal liability in respect of the complaint made under this section:

Provided that any amount paid to an accused person under this section shall be taken into account in awarding compensation to such person in any subsequent civil suit relating to the same matter.

h. Right to appeal

The person who has been ordered to pay compensation may appeal from the order, in so far as it relates to the payment of compensation, to the High Court.

i. Payment timing for compensation

When an order for payment of compensation to an accused person is made, the compensation shall not be paid to him before the period allowed for the presentation of the appeal has elapsed, or, if an appeal is presented, before the appeal has been decided.